

Separation of some co-existing industrial amino acids by normal and reversed phase thin layer chromatography on unconventional static phases

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Abstract : Chromatographic behaviour of four industrially important amino acids has been studied on plain and TAP impregnated adsorbent using DMSO-1 M HCl (1 : 1) as mobile phase. The unconventional adsorbents such as talc, alumina, starch and their admixtures have been used for chromatography. The effect of Vander Walls surface area (A_w) of the amino acids on their hR_f values has been discussed. Also, the effect of pI of these amino acids on hR_i (hR_f on unimpregnated layers - hR_f on impregnated layers) has been studied. Plain and impregnated alumina and talc-alumina layers were used to effect separations of these amino acids. The mechanism of migration is explained in terms of adsorption by and the polarity of the static phases used.

Keywords : Unconventional supports, RPTLC, DMSO, industrial amino acids.

Introduction

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) has been widely used for the analysis of products manufactured by the medical and microbiological industries. The advantages of this method are its simplicity, inexpensive instrumentation and high speed, the last of which is particularly important for performing series analysis. TLC can, however, be used when the possibilities of applying other methods are limited due to some properties of samples e.g. thermal lability, low volatility or the presence of considerable amounts of impurities, hampering the analysis as in case of resins, salts and pigments etc. Industrial amino acids such as L-lysine (Lys), L-threonine (Thr), L- β -phenyl alanine (β -Phe) and L-tryptophan (Trp) are widely used in medical practice, particularly in drugs for parenteral and per os feeding and also as food additives in cattle breeding and poultry farming¹.

Thin layer chromatography of amino acids on plain², impregnated³, modified⁴ silica gel-G layers and on unconventional supports⁵⁻⁸, has been carried out. Recently, TLC separation of Trp and its spectrophotometric determinations^{9,10} has also been achieved. As far as we are aware, the reversed phase thin layer chromatography (RPTLC) of these four industrial amino acids on unconventional supports such as talc, starch, alumina has not

been investigated and needs further study.

Talc, a natural hydrated magnesium silicate with resistance to acids, alkalies and heat has been used for normal and reversed phase thin layer chromatography (RPTLC) of organic substances⁶, amino acids⁷ and *d*-block metal ions¹¹. Owing to its hydrophobic nature, it has not been used as an adsorbent for TLC with aqueous media as mobile phases. Being inexpensive, talc has been chosen as an unconventional support besides common adsorbents such as starch, alumina and their admixtures. Starch and alumina have recently been used as TLC supports^{12,13}. In the present study, these adsorbents are used as such, as well as impregnated with triaryl phosphate (TAP) before use for the RPTLC of the four amino acids.

The advantage of using dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) as mobile phase in thin layer chromatographic separation of metal ions has long been established¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The dipolar aprotic solvent DMSO is a liquid over a wide temperature range, a strong electron donor and has fairly high dielectric constant (ϵ 47.5). It is, therefore, an excellent and selective solvent for many organic and even polymeric compounds and can enter into hydrogen bonding and dipole-dipole association. It has attracted the attention of researchers because of its biological applications and its unusual properties as solvent. But the same has

rarely been used as a mobile phase for the TLC separation of amino acids¹⁷. In order to further explore the separation potential of this solvent, we have decided to use DMSO-1 M HCl (1 : 1) as the mobile phase for the TLC and RPTLC of the four industrial amino acids on unconventional supports.

Results and discussion

Normal and reversed phase TLC has been performed for four industrial amino acids on talc, starch, alumina and their admixture layers in DMSO-1 M HCl (1 : 1) mobile phase. These amino acids gave compact spots and no tailing was observed. It is found that alumina and its admixture with talc being selective for amino acids is a better adsorbent for their separations. The amino acids were separated from synthetic mixtures on the basis of their selective adsorption and differential migration on these adsorbents. The separations achieved are given in Table 1. The physicochemical properties of the amino acids are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Important separations achieved (hR_f values are given in parentheses)

Adsorbent layer	Amino acid	Separated from
Alumina	Trp (26)	β -Phe (67), Lys (74)
	Thr (38)	β -Phe (65), Lys (72)
Impregnated alumina	β -Phe (4)	Thr (90), Lys (95)
	Trp (5)	Thr (92), Lys (95)
Talc-alumina	β -Phe (28)	Thr (95)
	Trp (32)	Thr (94)
Impregnated talc-alumina	β -Phe (17)	Thr (90)
	Trp (20)	Thr (88)

In order to study the retention behaviour of these amino acids, plots of hR_f vs A_w (Van der Walls surface area of amino acids) and hR_f vs pI (iso-electric point of amino acid) for various adsorbents were drawn (Figs. 1a-d and Fig. 2 respectively). A cursory inspection of the plots led to the following conclusions.

On talc layers :

It is evident from Fig. 1a that on talc layers, the amino acids exhibit higher hR_f which may be due to the fact that talc is almost non-polar and thus unable to retain the polar amino acids. The same is true for TAP impregnated talc layers as TAP impregnation does not significantly increase the non-polar nature of the talc layer. The mobile phase

Table 2. Physicochemical properties of amino acids

Sl. no.	Amino acid	Structure	Nature of R-groups	M_w	A_w	pI
1.	Thr (neutral)		Uncharged R-group	119	9.52	6.12
2.	β -Phe (neutral)		Aromatic R-group	165	12.05	5.48
3.	Trp (neutral)		Aromatic R-group	204	14.73	5.89
4.	Lys (basic)		Positively charged R-group	146	12.51	9.74

M_w = Molecular weight, A_w = Van der Walls surface area, pI = iso-electric point, R = side chain.

containing highly polar DMSO solvates the amino acids due to polar-polar interactions causing higher hR_f .

On starch layers :

Fig. 1b reveals that the amino acids are very slightly adsorbed on starch layers due to the solvation of amino acids by highly polar DMSO. Further, there is no significant difference in hR_f on plain and TAP impregnated starch layers. The starch layers contain many hydroxyl groups and are consequently hydrophilic in nature. But these hydroxyl groups do not interact with the amino acid molecules. Also, the TAP impregnation does not make the layers sufficiently non-polar and as such the phase reversal is not appreciably effected as desired. Thus, impregnation of starch layers has almost no effect on the retention behaviour of these amino acids.

On alumina layers :

Fig. 1c exhibits no definite trend on TAP impregnated alumina layers. Thr and Lys have much higher hR_f (≥ 90) due to less adsorption on these layers. The much lesser adsorption of Thr is probably due to it being polar in nature and also having smaller Van der Walls surface

Fig. 1. Plots of hR_f vs A_w for plain (-----) and impregnated (—) layers.

area. The -OH group present in it interacts with DMSO causing higher hR_f . For Lys, the polar side chain present in its molecule interacts with DMSO and is being solvated by it resulting in much higher hR_f . However, much lower hR_f for Trp is due to it being strongly adsorbed on account of larger Van der Waals surface area. β -Phe has almost non-polar phenyl ring in its molecule which does not interact with DMSO and as such the amino acid is not solvated by it resulting in almost zero hR_f . Larger molecular mass of β -Phe (M 165) also contributes to almost zero migration of the amino acid. On unimpregnated alumina layers, β -Phe and Lys have almost same hR_f probably due to having nearly same Van der Waals surface area (A_w). However, lower hR_f of Trp on plain as well as on TAP impregnated layers is attributed to its larger surface area and high molecular mass (M 204). The low hR_f for Thr on these layers is both due to smaller Van der Waals surface area as well as the specific interaction of the amino acid with unimpregnated alumina layers.

On talc-alumina layers :

The admixture of alumina with other adsorbents were used for TLC of amino acids, but significant results could not be achieved except in case of talc-alumina (1 : 1) layers (Fig. 1d). On these layers, the hR_f suddenly decreases with increase in the value of A_w of the amino acids. The much higher hR_f value of Thr on both the layers is due to the polar nature of its molecule which is easily solvated by the mobile phase due to polar-polar interaction. In contrast, the lower hR_f on both the layers for β -Phe and Trp is attributed to their non-polar or hydrophobic nature. Because of the presence of oxide ions, the surface of alumina is quite basic¹⁸ (estimated as approximately pH 12). However, the basic amino acid Lys also shows lower hR_f probably due to the presence of an extra -NH₂ group in its molecule which is having polar-polar interactions with the basic alumina surface resulting in greater adsorption of the amino acid on these layers. The other factor for the decrease in hR_f for Thr to β -Phe both on plain and impregnated layers is probably due to the increase in A_w causing higher adsorption.

Effect of pI on the hR_f values of amino acids :

To study the difference in the mobility behaviour of amino acids on plain and impregnated layers, hR_f data (hR_f on plain layers - hR_f on impregnated layers) for amino acids were plotted against pI (iso-electric point used to describe the charge character and polarities of the

amino acid) for different adsorbent layers (Fig. 2). The salient features are discussed below.

Fig. 2. Plots of hR_1 vs pI for amino acids.

Talc layers :

There is no significant difference in hR_1 values of the amino acids at different pI showing that impregnation has almost no effect on their retention behaviour except in case of β -Phe which is of least polar nature among all the four amino acids. The talc layers are almost non-polar and TAP impregnation does not significantly increase the non-polar nature of the layer.

Alumina layers :

The spots are more compact and more clearly visualized on these layers. β -Phe and Trp show significantly high positive hR_1 , whereas Thr and Lys has negative one. For β -Phe and Trp, this is probably due to the fact that these acids interact more strongly with impregnated adsorbent surface resulting in lower hR_f . In contrast, Thr and Lys are much strongly adsorbed on unimpregnated layers due to the polar nature of alumina surface. Thr being polar is strongly solvated by DMSO on almost non-polar TAP impregnated layers causing relatively higher hR_f . The same is true for slightly polar Lys which interacts with the mobile phase causing higher hR_f on impregnated layers.

Starch layers :

The hR_1 values of the amino acids are very low and there is no significant variation in it with increasing pI . It is probably due to the highly branched structure of starch, formed by amylose (linear polymer of α -D(+)-glucose)

and amylopectin (branched polymer of α -D(+)-glucose). Being a high molecular mass polymer and having a network structure, TAP impregnation does not make it sufficiently non-polar and consequently there is almost no effect of impregnation on hR_f values.

Talc-alumina layers :

The amino acids give positive hR_1 which clearly shows that impregnation reduces their mobility due to the decrease in the polarity of the layer. The slightly higher hR_1 for Lys is due to the presence of larger aliphatic side chain in it, which increases the basic nature of the acid resulting in lower hR_f on impregnated layers. The presence of an extra $-NH_2$ group and lone pair of electrons in its molecule is attributed to its basic nature.

Experimental

A horizontal chromatographic chamber was used for chromatography of amino acids. Glass plates (2.5×15 cm) were used as the support for thin layers. Commercial talc, alumina, starch (Qualigens fine chemicals, India) were used as adsorbents. Triarylphosphate (TAP) from LOBA and other chemicals (DMSO, HCl) were of analytical reagent grade. DMSO-1 M HCl (1 : 1) was used as mobile phase.

Talc was suspended in ethanol as a 1 : 1 (w/v) mixture. Slurries of starch and alumina were prepared as 1 : 3 (w/v) mixtures with distilled water. Mixtures 1 : 1 (w/w) of these adsorbents were prepared, stirred for 5 min and then immediately coated onto clean glass plates. The coated plates were first dried at room temperature and then in an electric oven at 100 ± 5 °C for 2 h. These were then impregnated with TAP by development with a solution of 5% TAP in benzene. After impregnation, plates were again dried at 90 ± 5 °C for 1 h and then stored in a desiccator before use.

The amino acids investigated were Thr, β -Phe, Lys and Trp. Standard solutions of individual amino acids and their mixtures were prepared having concentration 500 ng/ μ L in distilled water. A solution (0.2%) of ninhydrin in acetone was used for detection as reported earlier⁸.

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